

ARCHITECTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL PUBLIC CENTRES OF KHOREZM REGION (UZBEKISTAN)

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ABSTRACT

In the context of globalization, tourism has become one of the most important social, economic and cultural factors. Therefore, the planning and improvement of cultural and educational centers, especially in the Khorezm oasis, their social formation is becoming one of the most pressing issues today. This article represents the significance if the public places located in Khorezm Region.

Keywords- cultural and educational centers; historic city; compositional connections; architectural complex; Khorezm region.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to K. Levi Strauss, "where there is a rule, culture begins. All the commonalities in human nature belong to nature and are characterized by spontaneous automatism, and the qualities determined by the norms of coercion belong to the sphere of culture and embody relativity and individuality." . Therefore, as a branch of culture, the set of rules for cultural and educational centers is specified separately in the SHNK and KMK .

Our main goal is to develop design methods for the expression of the rich culture of Uzbekistan in modern buildings in the context of a historic city, including the identification of the main forms of architecture of Khorezm region.

It is necessary not to identify the artistic and cultural riches that have accumulated over the centuries, creating a unique image of Khorezm, but to include a new member among the new buildings. The percentage of ancient architecture in the general fund of Khorezm facilities is declining. The problem of the compositional connection of the new large-scale structure with the small ancient structures remains unresolved. With this in mind, our priority is to adapt and design the planned cultural and educational centers in Khorezm.

To achieve the above goal, you need to perform the following tasks:

- Study of the stages of development of architecture in Khorezm region;
- Study of issues in the form of cultural and educational architecture;

- Development of principles of construction planning.

II. MAIN PART

Urban planning in Khorezm, in particular, monumental architecture. av. From the middle of the 1st millennium BC. It was widely developed during the period up to the beginning of the 8th century. Large castles, especially the capital city (Tuproqqala, Kot), the regional temple (Hazarasp), mausoleums (Chirikrabort) and other types of community buildings were erected. There is a residence with 3 minarets, a magnificent royal palace (280 sq.m. area), handicraft houses and a market along the central streets. Various branches of handicrafts are highly developed in the city: pottery, blacksmithing, coppersmithing, armaments, jewellery, construction and textiles. Various artefacts found in the ruins of the castle, in particular, some pieces of fine art, clay sculptures, murals (a woman playing the flute, the goddess Nohid holding a pomegranate), landscapes and pottery sculptures, artistically made to a high standard. Length of wood and leather. The documents written in the Khorezmian script testified to the level of literacy, which was the basis of the spirituality of the people of the region.

In the early Middle Ages (4th-8th centuries) architecture flourished again, with castles, palaces and mansions (Burgutkala, Uyqala, Kumbosgan Castle, etc.) built in the shape of a square or rectangle, with strong circular towers at the corners. Among the castles and mansions built during this period, the architectural ones, especially Teshikkala and Yakka Porson, are noteworthy.

Historical and architectural monuments of Khorezm region are world-famous. There are 149 architectural and urban planning, 16 archeological, 21 monumental art and sculptural monuments in the region. The main part of the architectural monuments is located in Khiva. Part of its Ichan Fortress is included in the UNESCO World Heritage Cities List. Among the monuments in Khiva are the Juma Mosque (10th-18th centuries), the Pahlavon Mahmud Architectural Complex (14th-early 19th-early 20th centuries), the mausoleums of Sayyid Aloviddin (14th-18th centuries), the Three Saints (1549, 1821), and Tashkhovli (19th century), the palaces of the Old Ark (17th-19th centuries), the Muhammad Aminkhan Madrasa and Tower, and other attractions for visitors and travelers. There are also historical monuments in Khiva, Hazarasp, Khonka, Shovot, Yangiarik, Kushkopir, Bagat and other districts. Among them is the Chodra courtyard in Khiva district (18th-19th centuries), Shahimardon architectural complex (19th century), Qubla Tozabog Palace (1893–1913), Muzrabshah in Hazarasp (16th – 18th centuries), mausoleums of Sheikh Qasim Eshan (18th – 19th centuries), ancient Hazarasp fortress (6th millennium BC). 5th century), Said ota mosque in Khanka district (1766), Vayangan bobo mausoleum in Shovot district (16th-19th centuries); Sheikh Mukhtor Vali (Ostanabobo, 14a) architectural complex of Yangiarik district; Imoratbobo architectural complex of Kushkopir district (16th-19th centuries) and others.

During the years of independence, individual housing construction in the region has developed rapidly. The towns of Navruz and Kosmaabad, adjacent to the cities of Urgench

and Khiva, have been built. The Government of Uzbekistan pays great attention to the preservation and restoration of historical and architectural monuments in the region. On the eve of the 2,500th anniversary of the city of Khiva (1997), the 800th anniversary of Jalaliddin Manguberdi (1999), the 2700th anniversary of the Avesta book (2001), a large-scale repair of architectural monuments, landscaping and beautification of the area. Khorezm region was awarded the Order of Jaloliddin Manguberdi on August 22, 2003.

Figure 1. Urgench trade and cultural center

In order to provide modern services to tourists and improve the quality of services, a data center was launched at the initiative of the Department of Tourism Development of Khorezm region in the busiest area of the region "Ichan-Kala". Now our visitors to the territory of "Ichan-Kala" can get the necessary air tickets, train tickets and their reservations, get detailed information about hotels and reservations, restaurants, cafes, bars, bars, etc. maps, taxi services, guides and information on cultural events in the region.

Figure 2. The first design of Khiva was made in 1740

The city is 1,000 meters long and 400 meters wide and covers an area of 40 hectares. It is surrounded by a ditch. The city was accessible from the east by a special bridge. The bridge was raised at night. Starting from the gate near the bridge, the main street leads to the Ark Gate. The arch is located in the western part of the city. The main street of the city divides it into 2 parts (north and south). In the arch there is a khan's palace, a harem, an armory, which is specially surrounded by a castle wall. However, some buildings of that period were not included in the drawing. Another design of the city was drawn in 1839 by the topographer G.N. Zelenin, who came from Russia on a secret mission. According to G.N. Zelenin, the city had 17 mosques, 22 neighborhoods and 260 stalls at the time.

The city is the only one in Central Asia in terms of the integrity of the architectural ensemble. In 1967, for the first time in Central Asia, the Ichan fortress (county) of Khiva was declared a historical and architectural monument reserve. Khiva's place in the development of world culture was highlighted at the 28th session of the UNESCO General Conference (October-November 1995). By the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of January 3, 1996, the 2,500th anniversary of Khiva was widely celebrated in 1997.

In Khorezm there is a museum of traditional musicians named after the poet Khodzhikhon Boltaboev, in the city of Urgench there is a museum of applied art and history of Khorezm. All this greatly contributes to the development of the consciousness and spirituality of the people.

Figure 3. Bird-eye-view of Khiva city

The Khorezm Theater, the Agahi Khorezm Regional Musical Drama Theater, is one of the oldest theaters in Uzbekistan. 1922 It was organized on March 2 under the name "Government House" under the leadership of Hamza. It consists of 12 people (Safo Muganniy, KS Saroymonov, U. Kurban, R. Yusupov, O. Bekchurina, M. Yakubov (Sheroziy), K. Kutliev, M. Kharratov, Sh. Saloev, J. Kalantarov and others) The troupe began its work by staging small works. Hamza based his works on "The Servant with the Rich", "Punishment of Slanderers", "Poisonous Life", "Tragedies of Fergana", "Karmok", "Telephone", Mannon Uyghur's "Turkistan Doctor", Ghulam Zafari's "Children of Freedom" as the first performances, the leading roles were played by Masharif Polvonov, Yakub Devonov, Oysha Bekchurina, Khansky, Khanskaya and others. 1933 Due to the relocation of

the center of Khorezm to Urgench, the theater was relocated to Urgench and renamed the Khorezm District State Musical Drama Theater.

Based on the results of the study and the conclusions on the above-mentioned construction, the author intends to propose a project of a cultural and educational center.

The Cultural Enlightenment Center project is designed in accordance with the guidelines of the following normative documents.

1. KMK2.01.03-96 "Construction in seismic areas".
2. KMK 2.01.07-96 "Loads and Impacts".
3. SHNK 3.01.08-99 "Residential and Community Buildings"

The project used exterior photographs of unique public buildings. The interior of the complex is distinguished by its simplicity and the use of exterior and interior decoration materials, which belong to the modern, technical minimalism.

During the planning of various foggy buildings, there are changes in the shade of the sun during the day, which has a significant impact on the movement of air around the windows. The preservation of the microclimate is achieved through sunscreen mirrors.

During the project, the historical solutions are planned to be as convenient as possible for visitors and staff. For the territory of Khorezm - the main history of Khorezm was studied and implemented.

The auditorium of the center is designed for various events, meetings and performances, which are held from time to time. In addition, the hall can be used as a cinema. Because the hall also has its own movie projection rooms.

It should be noted that the center also has a library for readers. The library certainly has a wide, bright, rectangular shape. This, in turn, helps young people to study in comfortable conditions in their classrooms.

III. CONCLUSION

Today, there is a need to add international tourism and wholesale centers (trade at hippodromes) to the newly formed city-building (construction) staff. The importance of its

city-building has not been studied. Normative and methodological documents have not been developed in this area. However, it has a special place in the capitals and cities of the Republic and regions. For example, the problems of urban planning of the Republican wholesale trade center, the formation of buildings, transport facilities, roads and other infrastructure facilities have not been resolved.

If our historical cities are transformed into "open-air museums", the tourism potential of the country will be maximized, and at the same time, our historical cities will be passed on to the next generation. As a result, high opportunities are created for our artisans working in the country, which opens up a wide range of opportunities for their entrepreneurial activities, and the country.

demonstrates its rich cultural heritage to the world.

Khiva is one of the ancient cities of Khorezm and an incomparable jewel of medieval oriental architecture. Thousands of tourists visit Khiva every year to see its legendary beauty. The increase in the number of tourists from year to year requires further growth and improvement of the development of the industry.

Taking into account the cultural and historical-architectural monuments of Khorezm architecture, the principles of application of the historical heritage of the past in accordance with the methods of adaptation and study of architectural monuments were selected: - maximum preservation of the building; - Bringing the new function of the facility closer to historic buildings; - Inheritance of traditions of folk architecture. As mentioned above, it is necessary to determine the supporting nature of both individual buildings and architectural ensembles. Uzbekistan is proud of its ancient architectural monuments, and interest in them is growing year by year. The number of tourists is also growing from year to year. The number of foreign tourists has increased. Tourism is a new and promising business in the country, and the potential of Uzbekistan makes tourism an effective sector of the economy.

The inspection revealed the following factors influencing the choice of a new function for the building of the project of the cultural and educational center:

- group classification building; - Territorial historical biography of the object;
- Features of the project of the cultural center;
 - the need of the city for this or that functional group;
- Spatial and spatial and planning features of the building;
- Location of the facility in the urban structure.

The planning and compositional connection with the project of a large-scale cultural and educational center and its modern urban complex will also be taken into account.

-creation of modern convenience, application of modern principles of interior design (technological, functional zoning).

- adherence to the traditional principles of the region;

- Preservation of the principle of conformity of the nature of landscaping and landscaping of the territory of the monument to the functional, compositional and stylistic features of the building architecture.

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